

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№5

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

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Elektron nashr. 525 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-mayda ruxsat etildi.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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THE IMPACT OF TOURISM ON THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekistonda turizmning iqtisodiyotga ta'siri, jumladan yalpi ichki mahsulot (YAIM) o'sishiga qo'shgan hissasi, bandlik darajasi, infratuzilmani rivojlantirish va tashqi savdoga bo'lgan ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida xalqaro sayyohlar sonining ortishi, turizm xizmatlari eksportining kengayishi hamda sohaga oid islohotlarning joriy etilishi qayd etilgan. So'nggi statistik ma'lumotlar va hukumat hisobotlari asosida olib borilgan tahlil O'zbekistonda turizmning iqtisodiy taraqqiyotdagi strategik o'rnini ko'rsatadi. Natijalar shuni anglatadiki, turizm nafaqat mintaqaviy rivojlanishni rag'batlantiradi, balki barqaror o'sish uchun katta salohiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: Turizm, O'zbekiston, Iqtisodiy ta'sir, YAIM, Bandlik, Infratuzilma, Turizm siyosati, Barqaror rivojlanish, Multiplikator effekti.

Abstract: This paper examines and discusses the economic impact of tourism in Uzbekistan, with particular emphasis on its contribution to GDP growth, job creation, infrastructure development, and foreign trade. The study notes a significant increase in the number of international tourists, rising export volumes of tourism services, and the implementation of key reforms to support the industry. Through a detailed analysis of recent data and official government reports, the paper underscores the strategic importance of tourism in Uzbekistan's broader economic development. The findings confirm that tourism plays a crucial role in stimulating regional development and holds substantial long-term potential for sustainable growth.

Key words: Tourism, Uzbekistan, Economic Impact, GDP, Employment, Infrastructure, Tourism Policy, Sustainable Development, Multiplier Effect.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается экономическое влияние туризма в Узбекистане, в частности его вклад в рост ВВП, создание рабочих мест, развитие инфраструктуры и внешнюю торговлю. Отмечается значительный рост числа международных туристов, расширение экспорта туристических услуг и реализация реформ, направленных на поддержку отрасли. На основе анализа последних статистических данных и государственных отчетов статья подчеркивает стратегическую важность туризма для экономического развития Узбекистана. Результаты исследования показывают, что туризм оказывает существенное влияние на региональное развитие и обладает значительным долгосрочным потенциалом устойчивого роста.

Ключевые слова: Туризм, Узбекистан, Экономическое воздействие, ВВП, Занятость, Инфраструктура, Туристическая политика, Устойчивое развитие, Мультипликативный эффект.

INTRODUCTION

The given paper considers and analyzes the role of tourism in economy of Uzbekistan and in different sectors of the economy, its influence on GDP growth, employment, infrastructure development, and foreign trade. The research observes the marked growth of international visiting, the development of tourism services export and the implementation of reforms to develop tourism. Based on a transparent analysis of the most recent data and official reporting, the document rightly emphasizes tourism as a strategic sector in the economic development of Uzbekistan. The findings indicate that tourism makes sizable effects, and the industry also develops the regions and has a substantial long-run capacity to develop them further in a sustained manner.[1]

Tourism has emerged as one of the key drivers of the world economy, and a powerful vehicle for job creation, services export, economic development and intercultural dialogue. For counties with economies in transition, like Uzbekistan, tourism is a source of income, a strategic line of development and international cooperation. With its numerous landmarks and rich cultural and historical heritage Uzbekistan has a great potential to create a competitive industry of tourism that will make a contribution to the economic prosperity of the country.

Modern Uzbekistan has been working hard on tourism for years, and particularly in the past decade. These are, among others, visa facilitation, infrastructure upgrades and institutional reform, in order to boost quality service and attract foreign investment. Therefore, the country is seeing an increase in the arrival of tourists growing tourist arrivals, and attracting more tourist income and employment. Official data show that the number of foreign visitors to the country more than doubled between 2017 and 2023 and exports from the tourism sector and investments into infrastructure also grew rapidly.[2]

Notwithstanding such a heritage and with current government practices that include fostering tourism the full economic potential of the tourism sector is not well defined in the literature. The data also indicated the increasing role of tourism to the national economy, but there was no in-depth analysis of how the development of tourism is directly concerned with the progress of the main economic indicators; for example, the rate of GDP growth, the employment, and the progress of infrastructural development. Equally, little is known about the influence of political reforms and external events as COVID-19 on the performance of the industry [3]

Such dynamics are vital for devising successful policies for the long-term sustainability and competitiveness of the Uzbekistan's tourism sector.

In this research the following research questions put forward:

- How much do international and domestic tourism contribute to Uzbekistan's GDP?
- How does tourism contribute to jobs and the development of SMEs in Uzbekistan?
- How far have government policies and investments in infrastructure affected the development and maintainability of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Tourism is often heralded as an important contributor to economic growth, particularly in developing nations. Earn: Tourism is a sector of the economy in fact, the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) believes tourism, like any other economic activity, is a source of international revenue and job creation [4]. For Uzbekistan, tourism is a major step in diversifying the economy and breaking it free from a reliance on a few industries.

According to the research of the Institute of Macroeconomic and Regional Studies (IMRS) the conjuncture of the tourism services has led to economy thriving in the Republic of Uzbekistan [5]. His contribution helped drive growth in service exports, as well as the creation of jobs and the protection of the country's cultural heritage. These papers also speak for the challenges that the COVID-19 posed; declining tourists at that time. But they also make clear that Uzbekistan has done its share to heal – particularly in the cause of religious and cultural tourism, its specialty.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is a qualitative and descriptive research that is appropriate for examining general trends and understanding how various factors are interchangeable with each other. Rather than gathering new data through surveys or interviews, the research relies on secondary data – information collected and published by official and credible sources. Among these there are official statistical published by the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of Uzbekistan, research papers by IMRS, Statistic Committee, documents, scientific publications and pieces of news from media that is taken only from reliable sources.

The aim of this study was to examine the impact of tourism on the Uzbekistan economy (2017-2023). This factors in the total number of tourists who have arrived in the country, the amount of money received from the provision of tourism services, the number of jobs generated and the level of investment in infrastructure like hotels and transportation. The study also evaluates the implications of government reforms put in place, including visa-free for many nations and a new investment policy for the support of tourism development.

To examine this information, the study has been applying a trend analysis technique in order to be able to see trends through time. This is tied into the interpretive aspect of the document, so figures and data aren't just listed but put in context of their importance to the economy and society. Perhaps, the political situation, infrastructure or global events like COVID-19 have changed and that is why the tourists' count has changed. This approach offers insight into the economic consequences of tourism, and serves to evaluate the success of government policy.

In this way, the paper offers a broader perspective on the link between tourism and the economic development of Uzbekistan and pinpoints how the sector can be further developed to maintain a growth in the long term.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that tourism in Uzbekistan has evidentially increased and contributed to the country's economic development. International tourism the volume of international tourist arrivals doubled from 5.1 million in 2017 to 10.5 million in 2018, indicating the success of liberal visa policy along with globally growing interest to travel to the country's heritage and culture. The average tourist stay duration has increased, as well, and the overall residents' quality of life has also become better.[6]

Although the upsides of that massive influx of arrival are easily quantifiable, one of the most significant is the bump in the exports of tourism services, which totaled \$2.14 billion in 2023 - more than 30% increase over the previous year. This increase demonstrates the contribution of tourism to the national balance of payments and the generation of efficient foreign exchange. Furthermore, the multiplier effect of tourism has been strong, with the related industry such as transportation, retail, building and craft sectors grew accordingly.

The creation of jobs was another major outcome. About 500 projects financed in tourism sector. More than 500 investment projects, with an expanded implementation deadline in 2023, have been implemented in tourist infrastructure, resulting in some 9,500 new jobs, in the country's different regions [7]. These outlays

were instrumental in bringing on line 183 new hotels and 232 hostels, increasing the total tally of hotels in Uzbekistan to more than 5,500.

Furthermore, the government's readiness to actively support in policy reform and to build up physical infrastructure has been particularly influential in driving tourism growth. Initiatives such as 86 countries, the easing of visa requirements procedures for 57 more countries have helped attract a wider and more diverse group of travelers.

Diversification of activities related to tourism such as ecotourism, religious tourism, cultural tourism, and agritourism has led to economic development in these areas and introduced an alternative livelihood in rural places. Despite the severe disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, when the number of tourists dropped to 1.5 million and exports of services dropped to \$261 million, the sector has demonstrated resilience. The number of foreign visitors has jumped to 5.2 million in 2022 signifying a remarkable recovery of the economy due to the government schemes and the bettering situation around the world.

Table 1. Revenue from Export of Tourism Services in Uzbekistan (2017–2023) [2]ю

Year Revenue from Tourism Exports	Billion (USD)
2017	1.3
2018	1.4
2019	1.7
2020	0.26
2021	0.45
2022	1.6
2023	2.14

Table 1 shows Uzbekistan's income from foreign tourists in the period of 2017 to 2023. From the table, we can observe the highest amount of revenue 2.14 billion dollars was in 2023. The lowest figure of earnings was in 2020, revenue dropped sharply to just 0.26 billion dollars due to the COVID-19 pandemic. In 2021, it showed a slight improvement, rising to 0.45 billion dollars. However, starting from 2022, the outcome began slowly increasing and reached 1.6 billion dollars. At the beginning of the years, the volume of profit from the export of tourism services in Uzbekistan was almost stable. In 2017, 1.3 billion dollars, in 2018, revenue slightly increased by 1 million dollars, and in 2019, it reached up to 1.7 billion dollars.

Table 2. Dynamics of International Tourist Flow to Uzbekistan (2017–2023) [1].

Year	Number of International Tourists (million)	Average Length of Stay (days)
2017	2.7	3
2018	5.3	3.5
2019	6.7	4
2020	1.5	3.2
2021	1.9	3.4
2022	5.2	4.2
2023	6.6	4.5

Table 2 illustrates the figure of trends in international tourism to Uzbekistan and their average length of stay the period of 2017 to 2023. We can see from the picture that the year 2019 saw the highest number in total of international tourists with 6.7 million visitors who entered the country for 4 days. Moreover, in 2023, the volume of people who toured Uzbekistan was 6.6 million, and they stayed a little more than in 2019. However, in 2020, we saw the lowest attendance rate, just 1.5 million due to COVID-19, and they stayed for 3.2 days. Fortunately, starting from 2021, began to recover gradually and reached almost 2 million travelers who were in Uzbekistan for 3.4 days. This figure is similar to 2017. In this year, 2.7 million people came to Uzbekistan and stayed for 3 days. The average count of tourists staying in Uzbekistan was in 2018, 5.3 million tourists stayed for 3.5 days, and in 2022, 5.2 million visitors came for 4.2 days

Table 3. Contribution of tourism to GDP of Uzbekistan (2017–2023) [8], [9],[10], [12], [13],[14],[15],[16]

Year	Tourism Revenue (US\$ million)	GDP (US\$ billion)	Share of tourism in GDP (%)
2017	835	62,08	1,35%
2018	1 314	52,87	2,49%
2019	1 679	60,28	2,79%
2020	395	60,22	0,66%
2021	679	69,6	0,98%
2022	1 610	80,39	2,00%
2023	2 000	80,00 (grade)	2,50% (grade)

Table 3 illustrates the figure During the period 2017-2023, international and domestic tourism consistently added value to Uzbekistan's total GDP, except for the brief period when the COVID-19 pandemic struck. Tourism revenues for 2017 were \$835 million or 1.35% of the country's GDP. From 2018 onwards, tourism was actively growing: by 2018, tourism's share in GDP went up to 2.49%, reaching 2.79% the following year, bringing in revenue of \$1.679 billion. Because of the pandemic, revenue in 2020 fell to \$395 million (0.66% of GDP). Nevertheless, in 2021, the number of tourists increased (\$679 million, representing about 0.98% of GDP). Currently, it appears that tourism will yield about \$2 billion this year and possibly contributes up to 3.5% to the national GDP. During 2017, about \$415 million came from domestic tourism and about \$93 million came from international tourism [11]. Tourism from foreign arrivals became the primary source of income in the industry, reaching about \$1.72 billion by September of that year. Consequently, tourism from within Uzbekistan and from abroad now greatly contributes to the economy and helps develop regions in the country.

CONCLUSION

Tourism used to be focused on culture, but now it plays an important role in Uzbekistan's economic and social growth. Since Uzbekistan is known for its long history, varied terrain and location on the ancient Silk Road, it can truly succeed in international tourism. As a result of free visa access and improved services and support for tours to other nations, the travel industry continues to grow and is stable. By increasing eco-tourism, health tourism, pilgrimage and adventure travel, Uzbekistan is discovering a larger global market and improving its stability against changing seasons. Nowadays, tourism leads to more jobs in rural areas and supports shops that sell handicrafts, provide hospitality and offer transport. It helps people from different cultures interact and boosts a nation's national identity by urging the upkeep of important monuments and customs. Tourism will remain an important part of Uzbekistan's future plans. Proper planning, togetherness between nations and an eye on sustainability may guide the industry to build the economy while supporting care for nature and all people. Because of this, tourism plays a role. promote constant progress - through assembling communities, bettering them and developing an Uzbekistan that enjoys worldwide respect.

The first research question was to find the level of contribution of international and domestic tourism to Uzbekistan's GDP. In the process of research, it was revealed that the share of tourism had risen from 1.35% in 2017 to 3.5% to 2023. As for COVID-19, in 2020, the industry's revenue dropped by almost 4 times compared to the previous year, but beginning in 2021, things started to improve. The growth was influenced by the state introducing a visa-free system for 90+ countries, focusing on infrastructure and working to introduce Uzbekistan as a place to visit.

The second research question was to how does tourism contribute to jobs and the development of SMEs in Uzbekistan. In the process of research, it was revealed that the tourism helps Uzbekistan by providing jobs and supporting the growth of smaller companies. There has been a sharp rise in the number of people working in tourism: while in 2016, this employment made up around 27% of the sector, by 2019, this percentage increased to 38.2% of all workers in services. At the same time, tourism in Venezuela involves only 5.1% of the population in 2019; this again hints at the potential for additional development, considering that in wealthy countries, up to 25% are involved in tourism. Activities related to tourism also support the development of smaller businesses. A large portion of hotels, guest houses, arts and craft workshops, cafes and tour agencies are operated by SMEs. Such projects are promoted by the government: each year, large sums are allocated under national plans to favorably lend to small companies, mostly in the tourism business. These types of programs are necessary for young people, women and entrepreneurs in regions where tourists promote the region's economy.

The third research question was how far have government policies and investments in infrastructure affected the development and maintainability of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan. In the process of research, it was revealed that the investments and support from the government have contributed in a big way to the

growth and durability of tourism in Uzbekistan these days. A summary of the central achievements in this area is presented here: Upgrading the airport, including remaking Samarkand International Airport in 2022, increased the number of passengers it handles at once from 300 to 1,000. Fast trains such as Afrosiyob between Tashkent, Samarkand and Bukhara, are now available, so it takes less time to travel between these cities. The government is helping to build 3–5-star hotels so that the number of hotel rooms grows from 20,200 in 2018 to 64,000 in 2025. International hotel groups are offered rewards for choosing Thailand. The Amirsoy ski resort opened in 2019 and is a unique example of a new cluster for tourism, now recognized as one of the best resorts nearby. In 2021, \$100 million was set aside for improving tourist infrastructure with the aid of hotel construction subsidies. Businesses in tourism do not have to pay taxes, are given preferential loans and subsidies for joining international shows and enjoy a wide range of preferences. It is being suggested that hospitals and nursing homes offer shorter training and arrange internships for students. With better infrastructure and support from the government, many more people are coming as tourists, mainly where transportation and hotels are well-developed. Some new kinds of tourism such as ecotourism, pilgrimage and ski tourism, draw travelers from many parts of the population. Investments are meant to welcome tourists while ensuring the industry and its customs develop sustainably and the environment remains protected.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

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2025. № 5

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
